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This guide introduces readers to the fundamentals, essential developments, and complementary developments of ancient Egyptian kingship studies. Ancient Egyptian kingship, a complex facet of ancient Egyptian society, remains a topic of fascination for both scholars and the wider public. Its study, which has traditionally been based on royal sources, has most commonly focused on the nature of kings and other related topics, such as legitimacy and cosmology. However, in recent years scholars have started to recontextualize kingship within broader ancient Egyptian society, seeking to understand how the royal institution was engaged with by a variety of actors. This guide traces some of these developments in ancient Egyptian kingship studies, providing readers with an overview of the origins of scholarship and the current state of the field.

Ce guide introduit les lecteurs aux fondements, développements essentiels et complémentaires des études sur la royauté pharaonique. Facette complexe de la société égyptienne, la royauté constitue un objet d'étude qui continue de fasciner tant les chercheurs que le grand public. Son étude, traditionnellement fondée sur les sources royales, s'est le plus souvent concentrée sur la nature du roi et sur des problématiques connexes, comme la légitimité et la cosmologie. Toutefois, ces dernières années, des chercheurs ont entrepris de recontextualiser la royauté au sein de la société dans une perspective plus large, en cherchant à comprendre de quelle manière l'institution royale était investie par une diversité d'acteurs. Ce guide retrace ainsi quelques-uns de ces développements sur la royauté en Égypte ancienne et propose aux lecteurs un panorama qui s'étend des travaux pionniers aux recherches en cours.

Égypte ancienne, royauté, roi, institution royale
ancient Egypt, kingship, king, pharaoh, royal institution

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ncient Egyptian kingship was a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. Egyptian kings, who performed and enacted the duties of kingship, ruled—with significant interruptions to centralized power primarily, but not only, in the so-called Intermediate Periods—all of Egypt from circa 3300 BCE through to the Roman conquest. Though royal traditions and manifestations certainly changed throughout that time in significant ways, the institution remained consistent and recognizable to the Egyptians themselves. Now, these kings continue to capture the imagination of both scholars and the wider public. Ancient Egyptian kings and kingship have traditionally been approached through royal evidence, leading to studies focused on topics such as royal legitimacy and the nature of the king. Recently, scholars have become more interested in exploring the ways in which Egyptian kingship fit into broader ancient Egyptian society. To study kingship—not royal power, or royal legitimacy, or individual kings—means exploring the intricacies of the royal institution itself, which was generated and manifested not only by kings, but also by the royal family, officials, and non-royal actors.*

* This bibliographic guide is the product of thinking through the past and future of ancient Egyptian kingship studies with a fantastic group of colleagues: Niv Allon, Jessica Tomkins, Tara Prakash, Jonathan Winnerman, Julia Troche, and Jeffrey Newman. We are currently collaboratively working on an article on future avenues for the study of Egyptian kingship that further outlines several of the ideas summarily discussed here. This article will be the first output of a three-day workshop titled “The Future of Ancient Egyptian Kingship” held at the University of California, Irvine’s Steele-Burnand Anza-Borrego Desert Research Center in summer 2025. I am also happy to thank Jonathan Winnerman and Oren Siegel for their suggestions.

Sources in this guide are limited to those that either focus on kingship itself, or which more broadly provide new avenues for the research of kingship. Related topics, such as individual royal motifs or texts, royal monuments, or the particularities of individual reigns have all been broadly studied and could all have their own bibliographic guides. Even so, works that contribute to ancient Egyptian kingship studies are numerous; the goal of this guide is not to be comprehensive, but rather to highlight works that can provide interested readers with an overall grasp of the origins and evolving nature of ancient Egyptian kingship studies. It is important to note that other scholars of ancient Egyptian kingship would likely come up with lists quite different from this one, if asked, and that this guide derives from my own research into the topic.

Fundamentals

Early explorations of ancient Egyptian kingship, some of the main ones of which are cited here, usually focused on the nature of the king and questions of legitimacy and cosmology. Frankfort 1948, which has since its publication been largely questioned in Egyptology itself, remains the most influential treatment of Egyptian kingship outside the field, still being cited today in comparative works. Frankfort's book—which in fact is about Near Eastern kingship more broadly—largely focused on royal evidence and religious texts, resulting in a narrow focus on the Egyptian king's supposed divinity. Posener 1960 also predominantly examines the nature of the king but from the opposite perspective, in many ways responding to Frankfort directly. Indeed, using a wider array of texts, he argued against the divinity of the king, emphasizing the human aspect of kingship instead. In the same year as Posener, Goedicke published a book focused on only

Old Kingdom kingship and only non-royal, or private, texts. His conclusions, which can be thought of as a middle ground of sorts between Frankfort and Posener, emphasized that the body of the king was human while the office of kingship was divine. This debate culminated in 1985 with Bell's work on the royal *ka*, which used theories of medieval political theology to reconcile the divine and human aspects of the Egyptian king.

Already quite early in the study of ancient Egyptian kingship, then, we can see different sources and approaches being used by scholars, though research questions remained mostly focused on the nature of the king and kingship; there was not much attention given to how kingship and kings might have interacted with broader parts of Egyptian society. O'Connor and Silverman's edited volume from 1995, which continues to be often cited by scholars working on Egyptian kingship, can in many ways be seen as a culmination of these earlier studies. While not meant as a comprehensive treatment of Egyptian kingship, the volume has largely been treated as such. The focus of the chapters remains royal evidence, royal ideology, and royal legitimacy—topics that still dominate the study of ancient Egyptian kingship in 2026, with Egyptology largely continuing to accept the assumed centrality of kingship implicitly (and sometimes explicitly) espoused in these early works more than thirty years later.

■ Frankfort, Henri. 1948. *Kingship and the Gods: A Study of Ancient Near Eastern Religion as the Integration of Society and Nature*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press. [U. Chicago, ISAC \(1978's edition\)](#)

■ Posener, Georges. 1960. *De la divinité du pharaon*. Paris: Imprimerie nationale. [BnF, Gallica](#)

- Goedicke, Hans. 1960. *Die Stellung des Königs im Alten Reich*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Bell, Lanny. 1985. “Luxor Temple and the Cult of the Royal Ka.” *Journal of Near Eastern Studies* 44 (4): 251–94. [10.1086/373148](#)
- O’Connor, David, and David Silverman, eds. 1995. *Ancient Egyptian Kingship*. Leiden: Brill.

Essential Developments

Recently, scholars have become more interested in going beyond narrow questions of the nature of kings to better understand the practicalities of kingship and how it operated on the ground. The sources cited here are again not meant to be comprehensive, but they represent essential developments in the study of Egyptian kingship and, critically, offer avenues for future work. Already in 1999, Quirke considered the visibility (or lack thereof) of kings in Middle Kingdom administrative papyri from Lahun; his conclusions focused on the ritualized presence of the king in these texts, as well as his divine nature. In 2013, Bárta demonstrated the feasibility of studying kingship through non-royal sources—specifically Old Kingdom elite tombs—in what he called a “profane” approach. However, at the end of his study he claimed that the “inherent weakness” of such an approach to kingship is that its conclusions can diverge from the picture derived from royal sources. Subsequent studies, however,

have demonstrated the opposite: that such approaches have immense potential to nuance our modern understanding of Egyptian kingship.

For instance, Moreno García's 2019 book, which is an analysis of the ancient Egyptian state rather than kingship itself, makes it clear that different sectors of the Egyptian population affected and contributed to the functioning of society. Most importantly for the purposes of this guide, this study clearly demonstrates that the ancient Egyptian state was not equivalent to the king, a view present in many studies of Egyptian kingship following similar statements in O'Connor and Silverman 1995. Baines 2021 is an important work that rethinks the centrality of the king and kingship when it comes to religious practices. Rather than accepting the Egyptological truism that the king was the sole priest, Baines successfully argues against the omnipotence of the king in this arena. Troche 2021 adds to the new wave of Egyptological scholarship that questions the centrality of the king by exploring negotiations of power between the king and non-royal actors in the Old and Middle Kingdoms, primarily in the funerary realm. Going back to questions of the nature of the king, Winnerman 2023 provides a corrective to Bell 1985, demonstrating that the theory of the royal ka needs reexamination and that the question of the nature of the king needs to be further nuanced and recontextualized in the Egyptian evidence. Lastly, Bussmann 2023—a new textbook of Egyptian archaeology of the Old and Middle Kingdoms—makes evident both how possible and effective it can be to speak of ancient Egypt without giving kings primacy. This book, which will likely be used to teach future generations of Egyptologists, is emblematic of the ways in which Egyptology is shifting in its

frameworks of analysis. When it comes to kingship, both Bussmann 2023 and the other sources in this section represent exciting future avenues of study, all which go beyond questions of the divinity or lack thereof of kings to better understand how they, and kingship itself, fit into the broader social, religious, economic, and political landscapes of ancient Egypt.

- Quirke, Stephen. 1999. “Visible and invisible: the king in the administrative papyri of the late Middle Kingdom.” In *Das frühe ägyptische Königtum: Akten des 2. Symposiums zur ägyptischen Königsideologie in Wien, 24.-26.9.1997*, edited by Rolf Gundlach and Wilfried Seipel, 63–71. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Bárta, Miroslav. 2013. “Egyptian Kingship during the Old Kingdom.” In *Experiencing Power, Generating Authority: Cosmos, Politics, and the Ideology of Kingship in Ancient Egypt and Mesopotamia*, edited by Jane A. Hill, Philip Jones, and Antonio J. Morales, 257–283. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology.
- Moreno García, Juan Carlos. 2019. *The State in Ancient Egypt: Power, Challenges and Dynamics*. London: Bloomsbury.
- Baines, John. 2021. “Was the King of Egypt the Sole Qualified Priest of the Gods?.” In *Questionner le sphinx: mélanges offerts à Christiane Zivie-Coche*, edited by Philippe Collombert, Laurent Coulon, Ivan Guerneur, and Christophe Thiers, 1, 73–97 (Bibliothèque d’étude 178). Cairo: Institut français d’archéologie orientale.

- Troche, Julia. 2021. *Death, Power, and Apotheosis in Ancient Egypt*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- Bussmann, Richard. 2023. *The Archaeology of Pharaonic Egypt: Society and Culture, 2700-1700 BC*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Winnerman, Johnathan. 2023. “Divine Kingship and the Royal Ka.” In *Ancient Egyptian Society: Challenging Assumptions, Exploring Approaches*, edited by Kathlyn M. Cooney, Danielle Candelora, and Nadia Ben-Marzouk, 40–48. London: Routledge.

Complementary Developments

The sources in this section do not fully rethink kingship or its intersections with broader ancient Egyptian society; rather, they add further nuance to many of the topics discussed above, including the ways in which kings performed royal power, the potential divinity of the king, and comparative approaches to Egyptian kingship. This list is once again not comprehensive but rather meant to highlight other developments in ancient Egyptian kingship studies.

When it comes to earlier scholarship, Hornung 1983 provides a refreshing change from some other contemporary studies of Egyptian kingship, which primarily focused on questions regarding the nature of the king and the divine vs. human dichotomy. This article represents an attempt to understand how kingship was performed by the king in different contexts, though such performances remain confined to the realm of religious rituals. Leprohon 2013 is significant for its detailed treatment of the development of the royal titulary; it is a

study that can serve as the basis for further explorations of royal ideology and royal power from a royal perspective throughout Egyptian history. Bács and Beinlich 2017 has some useful chapters on the different ways in which royal authority was expressed in distinct contexts (both in Egypt and Nubia); it is cited here mostly for its publication in the series of conference proceedings *Symposium zur ägyptischen Königsideologie*. Though many of their chapters remain focused on royal evidence and top-down approaches, these volumes provide rich studies of various aspects of themes related to ancient Egyptian kingship, including royal palaces, royal ideology, and royal rituals. Bickel 2024 continues to focus on questions of the nature of the king but does so by employing theoretical frameworks from outside Egyptology, specifically cross-disciplinary ideas of sacred kingship, to argue that New Kingdom kings were made into gods through coronation rituals. This publication demonstrates both some of the ways in which ancient Egyptian kingship studies could add to and benefit from wider studies of kingship, as well as some of the dangers of importing models from outside of Egypt to study Egyptian kings. Bickel 2024 was published in a special issue of *Orient* titled “Current Studies in Ancient Egyptian Kingship,” though most of the articles in the volume do not in fact pertain to kingship itself. Nonetheless, the special issue highlights the continuing interest in the topic.

Hill et al. 2013 and Thompson and Tomkins 2025 are significant milestones in the study of ancient Egyptian kingship through a comparative perspective. Chapters in Hill, Jones, and Morales 2013 discuss Egyptian and Mesopotamian kingship through three main lenses: kingship and cosmos, kingship and politics, and kingship and landscape. These sections highlight that the focus of this volume

is importantly not confined to the nature of kings, but that it also considers how kingship worked politically and how its monumental presence transformed landscapes. Thompson and Tomkins 2025 examine power in ancient Egypt and the ancient Near East. Though not directly about kingship, the chapters in this volume work to better define “power,” a term often used in studies of ancient Egyptian kingship without definition, and in doing so advance the conversation about the functioning of kings in broader ancient Egyptian society.

■ Hornung, Erik. 1983. “Pharao ludens.” In *Das Spiel der Götter und der Menschen / The play of gods and men / Le jeu des hommes et des dieux*, edited by Rudolf Ritsema, 479–516. Frankfurt am Main: Insel.

■ Hill, Jane A., Philip Jones, and Antonio J. Morales, eds. 2013. *Experiencing Power, Generating Authority: Cosmos, Politics, and the Ideology of Kingship in Ancient Egypt and Mesopotamia*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology.

■ Leprohon, Ronald J. 2013. *The Great Name: Ancient Egyptian Royal Titulary*. Atlanta: Society of Biblical Literature.

■ Bács, Tamas, and Horst Beinlich, eds. 2017. *Constructing Authority: Prestige, Reputation and the Perception of Power in Egyptian Kingship*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

■ Bickel, Susanne. 2024. “Kings as Gods in the New Kingdom.” *Orient* 59: 37-57. [10.5356/orient.59.37](https://doi.org/10.5356/orient.59.37)

■ Thompson, Shane M., and Jessica Tomkins, eds. 2025. *Understanding Power in Ancient Egypt and the Near East, Volume I: Approaches*. Leiden: Brill.